

PUBLIC SYSTEM OF DIGITAL BOOKKEEPING SYSTEM (PSDB): PERCEPTIONS, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7523490

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Abstract: The present study related to the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB) and some of its main instruments concepts, digital bookkeeping (ECD), digital book keeping (EFD) and the Electronic Invoice (NF-e). Thus we sought to know the perception of the accounting profession in relation to adjustments and difficulties encountered in the implementation and operation of this system. In preparing this article we used the exploratory descriptive research and as procedures for conducting the survey were employed the survey method and literature as to the approach to the problem it is classified as qualitative. Also as a mechanism for data collection was performed using a questionnaire and the analysis was made through the investigation of the content. Knowing that it is an irreversible and even with all the difficulties of adaptation and adjustment process it was found that these professionals realize the importance of PSDB and are seeking to adapt and prepare to face the new challenges.

Keywords: Accounting. Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB). Opportunities. Challenges.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, most people use some type of technology to develop their activities, whether professional or not, and the accounting area could not be different. PSDB came with this purpose, to modernize and transform the current accounting system.

Considered a revolution in the accounting area, the Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB) modernized the way taxpayers provide information to tax administrations and inspection bodies, as its name suggests, it transforms all accounting documentation from the physical environment into digital files, transmitting them directly to

Organs interested bodies, using digital certification to validate and sign the documents. (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; PORDEUS; STROPARO, 2021; PRZYBYCZEWSKI; STROPARO, 2021; RAMOS; STROPARO; CORDEIRO, 2021; SANTIN; STROPARO, 2022).

It was instituted by Decree nº 6,022 of January 22, 2007 and is considered an integral system of the Growth Acceleration Program (PAC) 2007-2010, in the topic that concerns the measures aimed at improving and reducing the burden of the tax system (SILVA et al. al, 2018; SABIN; STROPARO, 2015).

It is in this scenario that the process by which accounting professionals are having to adapt due to the changes that are taking place was approached, today one cannot have that mistaken view that accounting is only concerned with meeting the requirements of the tax authorities , it is an important source of information that aims to help its users. (WESSLING, 2011)

In this way, the point of view of the accountants themselves was used to understand this new and dynamic environment in which they live. It was observed in this research whether in the work environment of these professionals there is an adequate technological structure to comply with the PSDB requirements and how the new routines that have been implemented by the system are adapting, considering that these changes do not only involve accountants, but also the companies, which are responsible for providing the information necessary for the fulfillment of ancillary obligations. Therefore, the guiding question of the research is what is the perception of accounting professionals regarding PSDB due to the adaptations, difficulties and opportunities encountered?

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

This section describes the general concepts of PSDB, emphasizing the main tools that integrate this system, digital bookkeeping (ECD), digital tax bookkeeping (EFD) and electronic invoice (NF-e).

Public System of Digital Bookkeeping System (PSDB)

Accounting is in constant technological evolution. It is currently undergoing changes, in which to ensure modernization, parameterization of information is essential, making it more accurate and more relevant (KSCHEVY; STROPARO, 2022; KOHUT; STROPARO, 2022; STROPARO, DOMBROSKI, 2018; SABIN; STROPARO, 2015; CHEN et al, 2006).

PSDB is an initiative of the federal government together with other institutional partners, and is based on the experience of electronic governments in other countries, such as Spain, Chile and Mexico. Its purpose is to bring the tax authorities closer to their taxpayers, modernizing the entire system of accounting activities and improving fiscal control. Allied to technological evolution, the expansion of communication through the internet and accounting procedures, on January 22, 2007, the Federal Government instituted, by Decree No. , 2007)

The PSDB project has the following main objectives: to promote the integration of tax authorities, rationalize and standardize ancillary obligations for taxpayers and speed up the identification of tax offenses. (BRASIL, 2014).

Prior to the implementation of PSDB, the taxpayer was required to send various information, often repeated, to several different bodies and following the rules stipulated by each of them. Through the total implementation of this system, the taxpayer starts to relate only to the PSDB, that is, he will send all the necessary information to a single database, which will be responsible for sharing it with the appropriate bodies.

Based on the modernization of the systematic fulfillment of ancillary obligations and taking advantage of the technology and practicality that the internet offers in terms of communication these days, PSDB started with three major projects, ECD, EFD and NF- and. Currently, PSDB has many other projects under development, which in the future will be in full operation, among them is being studied: e-Lalur, EFD Contributions, E-Social and the Central de Balanços.

All projects aim to extinguish the process done on paper to a digital format that can be shared online in a single database, so that all agencies can have access. It should be noted that each project has its rules and its specific public, so each taxpayer will be obliged to provide the information in the form and period that the legislation specifies for each case. In view of its benefits, the importance of PSDB within accounting is evident, the changes are not only impacting operational issues, but also represent a change in culture with the use of new information technologies.

Digital Accounting Bookkeeping (ECD)

The ECD is one of the tools that make up the PSDB, and its purpose is to replace paper bookkeeping with digital bookkeeping, with the obligation to transmit the following books: daily book, ledger and daily trial balance book, balance sheets and entry forms supporting the settlements transcribed in them.

In this way, the company obliged to adopt the ECD must, through an accounting system, generate and transmit the digital file containing all the books stipulated in the legislation, noting that the transmission is carried out through a system provided by PSDB, called PVA, which has the function of validating and digitally signing the document.

Due to the divergences of the various norms that deal with the subject, this file can be called Digital Daily Book, Digital Accounting Bookkeeping - ECD, Accounting Bookkeeping in electronic form or simply Accounting PSDB.

Digital Tax Bookkeeping (EFD) - EFD-ICMS/IPI

The EFD is another tool that makes up the PSDB, it is responsible for the bookkeeping related to the ICMS/IPI and also uses the system of transforming all processes and documents into digital format, “it consists of a set of bookkeeping of tax documents and of other information of interest to the tax authorities of the federated units and the Federal Revenue Service of Brazil” (RFB, 2012).

The company must generate a digital file from its database containing all the information of interest to the tax authorities regarding the period for calculating ICMS and IPI taxes, in the same way as the ECD, this file must be validated and signed through the program PVA, the obligation of EFD is determined by the legislation of each State.

The taxpayer must use the EFD-ICMS/IPI to carry out the bookkeeping of the following books: entry register book, output register book, inventory register book, IPI calculation register book and ICMS calculation register book.

Electronic Invoice (NF-E)

According to the RFB, the NF-e was developed in an integrated manner by the Treasury Departments of the States and the Federal Revenue Secretariat of Brazil, from the signing of Protocol ENAT 03/2005 (27/08/2005), which attributes to the National Meeting of State Tax Coordinators and Administrators (ENCAT) coordination and responsibility for the development and implementation of the NF-e Project.

It aimed to implement a model of electronic tax document with national coverage that replaces the issuance of the traditional paper invoice, types 1 and 1A, with legal validity and guarantee of security through the digital signature of the issuer, also simplifying the process issue of invoices and made it possible for the tax authorities to monitor commercial operations in real time. In this way, the NF-e can be used in all situations provided for in the rules, which

include: the entry and exit invoice, import operations, export operations, interstate operations or even simple remittance operations.

METHODOLOGY

According to Gil (2002, p. 17) research can be defined “as the rational and systematic procedure that aims to provide answers to the problems that are proposed”. This study used the inductive method as a logical basis for investigating the facts. To meet the requirements of this research, regarding the objectives, this study is classified as exploratory and descriptive.

In this way, a description was made of the perception of accounting professionals around PSDB, in order to collect information and interpret them, noting that there should be no interference from the researcher in the phenomenon that is being analyzed.

As for the procedures, bibliographical research and a survey were used to collect the data exposed in this study, in the same line of thought. The qualitative method makes it possible to understand and analyze the interaction of the population involved in the research with regard to the phenomenon addressed, perceiving the environment in which the facts occur.

As for the population or universe of this research, it is formed by all professionals in the accounting area, belonging to the jurisdiction of the Delegacia do Conselho Regional de Contabilidade do Paraná (CRCPR) in the city of Irati-PR, which has the following cities in its circumscription: Fernandes Pinheiro, Imbituva, Inácio Martins, Irati, Mallet, Rebouças, Rio Azul, São João do Triunfo and Teixeira Soares, among the total population, according to the CRC, there are 313 (three hundred and thirteen) professionals with active record.

As a sampling technique, intentional non-probabilistic was used for accessibility or convenience and covered 28 respondents. As a research tool, a questionnaire structured in blocks was used, with the purpose of obtaining answers to the research objectives and adequately responding to the guiding question, covering questions related to the characterization of the interviewees' profile, difficulties and adjustments necessary for the implementation of PSDB.

Regarding the form of application of the questionnaire, it was prepared with a Google® tool called forms and hosted on its own server.

The access address was made available via email via direct mail through the Association of Accountants of Irati, thus providing ease and security to respondents. It contains closed questions, which were largely formulated using the *Likert scale*.

As a form of interpretation, the method of content analysis was used, which aims to verify what is being said about a given subject, in content analysis the researcher tries to build

knowledge through textual observation, in this way he works traditionally with written materials.

DATA PRESENTATION

The present research had accounting professionals as its target audience, among the respondents 50% are male and 50% are female, 71% of respondents are between 18 and 40 years old and 28% are over 41 years old, it was also evidenced that 74% have higher education, noting that most of these have some type of specialization, representing 46%.

It was found that 59% work for more than 5 years as a professional in the accounting area, 58% are accountants, 8% are accounting technicians and 35% perform other functions, the respondents also reported that 70% of the professionals who operate the PSDB are accountants.

The following table deals with the adjustments necessary for the adoption of PSDB:

Table 1 - Necessary adjustments for the adoption of PSDB

	I agree	partially agree	I do not agree nor disagree	partially disagree	I disagree
Invest in improving the technological infrastructure.	71%	21%	4%	4%	0%
Adaptation of accounting software in accordance with legislation and standards established by PSDB	82%	11%	0%	0%	7%
The deadlines for adequacy are insufficient.	21%	39%	11%	18%	11%

Source: Research data

When it comes to modernization, as PSDB has been proposing, there is no doubt about the investment in improving technological tools, it needs to be aligned with the evolution of these systems.

Table 1 shows that 92% of the respondents totally or partially agree with the need to invest in improvements to the technological infrastructure, 4% neither agree nor disagree and 4% of the interviewees partially disagreed.

Regarding accounting software, most professionals already use integrated systems in their work environment, however, many of these programs are not standardized with PSDB, this question showed that 82% of respondents agree with the need to adapt accounting software in compliance with legislation and standards established by PSDB and only 7% disagree with this need.

As for the deadlines for PSDB adjustments, 21% of respondents agree that they are insufficient, likewise 39% partially agree and 11% neither agree nor disagree. Of the remaining respondents, 18% partially disagree and 11% disagree with this statement.

Regarding the difficulties related to PSDB, it can be seen in table 2:

Table 2 - Difficulties related to PSDB

	I agree	partially agree	I do not agree nor disagree	partially disagree	I disagree
The ERP (Integrated Information System) of the companies does not meet the technical standards of the PSDB, implying in reprocessing work to regularize the bookkeeping.	32%	36%	7%	18%	7%
Large amount of information to be fed into the system.	64%	21%	11%	0%	4%
Complexity for the interpretation of the legislation.	57%	36%	4%	4%	0%

Source: Research data

In order to feed the PSDB, accounting professionals depend on the information provided by the companies, which must deliver them with the standards established by the system, however, it was found that 68% of the interviewees totally or partially agree that the ERPs (integrated information system) of companies do not meet the technical standards established by PSDB, thus implying work reprocessing to regularize bookkeeping.

Another difficulty factor is the large volume of information that must be entered into the system, which demands time and attention from accountants, 64% of respondents agree that the amount of information is relatively high, likewise 21% of these partially agree, 11 % neither agree nor disagree and 4% disagree with the statement.

Finally, respondents were asked about the complexity of interpreting the legislation, laws, norms, decrees, normative acts, instructions and other texts are created daily in order to regulate certain activities.

Generally, they have a very technical content, sometimes difficult to understand, thus it was observed that 93% of professionals totally or partially agree that they encounter difficulties and consider the texts of the legislation complex.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This research sought to verify the perception of accounting professionals about PSDB, raising the adjustments that are being necessary and the difficulties they encounter in its

operation. For that, a questionnaire was applied to 28 professionals in the area, which led to obtaining the necessary information to achieve the objective of this study.

PSDB is no longer a novelty, but it is always adapting new tools with the aim of modernizing the entire current system for complying with ancillary obligations, and the trend for the near future is that all accounting routines will be integrated into this system.

There are indications that the younger public has greater ease and relates better to new technologies, since most respondents are up to 40 years old. However, it is not possible to correlate age groups over 40 with access to technology. On the other hand, investments in technological infrastructure are essential, as it can provide more agility and precision in obtaining information, accessing systems and processes in general.

Regarding the constant adaptations of accounting software, accounting professionals attest that they are important and that they must comply with the standards established by PSDB. What justifies this fact is the constant improvement of the system and development companies may have difficulties in keeping up with changes in real time.

PSDB continues to evolve constantly and its implementation has been taking place gradually, so all companies will have to adapt to the new system regardless of their size or billing, and one of the obstacles will be the poor structure of companies, especially in medium and small companies, as that have great difficulties in computerizing their processes and treating them in an integrated way.

At this time, the accounting professional will play an important role and it will be through him, together with the managers, directors and administrators, that measures will be adopted to comply with the requirements of the tax authorities and adjust to the standards established by the system.

It is concluded that despite so many adjustments and some difficulties, it must be considered that this whole process is necessary, however, it is noted that professionals are aware of all these transformations and are seeking to adapt and prepare to face the new challenges. .

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